

FORMATION OF PRAGMATIC COMPETENCES OF STUDENTS - AS A
PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

Rustam Yuldoshev Dilshod o'gli

Karshi state university Pedagogy faculty, support doctoral student

Annotation. Article own into in students pragmatic formation of competence and him improvement technologies about theoretical and practical actions about information takes and them analysis does Also students pragmatic meanings understanding and development with engage in in detail explained.

Key words: pragmatic competence, structure, pragmatic competence develop, modernization, important value, education process, education quality assessment, language of teaching main purpose.

In the world demand pragmatic competence development methodology improvement efficient technologies education to the process app is reaching Innovative education conditions Future of teachers pragmatic competence development methodology of improvement mechanisms work output, innovative programs based on multimedia electron resources Create and education quality evaluation according to wide wide affairs take is going Such affairs with together, education quality evaluation process and tools improvement, achieved the results determination enable giver mechanisms to practice current achieve ", students knowledge level international standards based on evaluation and English language science o ' school quality to increase about trends to practice app reach works take is going

It is known that the world across study environment, usually to the teachers directed become students pragmatic meanings understanding and development with when engaged in study program language practice lightening for lessons duration minimum time with perform for Created. And real in the world the conversation guess who does situations being studied from the language use possibilities limited. That's it because of I speak a foreign language in teaching pragmatic of competence integration research to do start importance I understood. The language of learning final purpose communication that it was because of this to the goal contribution adding studies pragmatism through transfer is important the world higher education in institutions innovative education future of teachers pragmatic competence development Methodical preparation quality provision, education process modeling, designing, teachers information technologies based on Methodical preparation improvement of students scientific competence increase according to scientific studies take is going That's it in terms of, future of teachers pragmatic competence development methodology improvement Methodical to the degree raising, development level diagnosis done increase, modular education to the road put, information communicativeness activation, future of the teacher professionalism determination according to scientific studies separately importance occupation is doing.

Modern education institutions social active. creative to thinking have person, graduates information to the flow directed qualifications to form, new technologies mastery, independent education is available knowledge deepening and to expand own to the front put

Pragmatic competence - of a person statement (said, written construct an idea) rules interpretation to do and application, statements (opinions) are different communicative functions

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-5

for of communicants (communication) characteristics of the participants and of communication social and cultural to the context according to respectively apply ability is considered

It should be noted that during the last few decades, a number of different models have appeared that describe pragmatic phenomena to one degree or another. Although they differ from each other with their individual perspectives, they have a number of common (common) properties, sides. First of all, the duality of these models is related to the structure. This means that in all such models there is some linguistic (linguistic) or otherwise grammatical component that constitutes the direct code of the statement.

Depending on the purpose of communication, the focus on the contextual use of language (reliance, intendedness) serves as the second component. Bidirectionality of such context and meaning dependence of pragmatic competence is present in all models. observed. This foreign to the language being taught tah c year of recipients pragmatic competence of formation importance shows.

Foreign in the language communicative of competence structural part as pragmatic of competence component composition the following elements into takes:

A. Social component (communication social contexts and communication of participants social roles interpretation do it get ability ; of communication social acceptable style choose get ability);

B. Socio-linguistic (sociolinguistic) component (interlocutor social figure portrait Create for speech statement (social meanings of the register variations and modality) interpretation to do ability)); communication to the goal selected social to roles according to reach for necessary language and speech of means use ability));

C. socio-cultural component (the ability to interpret the information received about the mother tongue and the cultural aspect of the countries of the intended (learned) language in the conditions of intercultural interpersonal interaction;

D. speech component (the ability to interpret the choice of speech genres made by the interlocutor, the cohesion and coherence of the speech statement; the ability to choose and implement speech communication in accordance with the rules of construction of speech communication for the performance of communicative tasks; d) compensatory component (repetition, accuracy /clarification, the ability to fill the gaps and gaps in language and socio-cultural issues by using information - reference in order to make and organize the evaluation relationship to the expressed thought/statement, it is carried out on the basis of teaching the sum of lexical, grammatical and syntactic units of the language. In the research work, four groups of markers are proposed: basic/basic (lexical, mixed, syntactic), descriptive, parallel (vocative), protest expression markers) and discussion and discursive (contrastive, elaborative, inferential, topic change markers). First, we define pragmatics as a central element of pragmatic competence. Pragmatics is the study of how language is used in communication, paying more attention to how it is said rather than what(s) is said. American philosopher Ch. Posted by Morris. The philosopher studied it as a component of semiotics along with semantics and syntax.

The notion that promoting pragmatic competence should begin with increasing the pragmatic awareness of both students and teachers has been at the center of many discussions. Bardovi-Harlig argues that pragmatic awareness should be one of the goals of classroom instruction. If both language learners and teachers realize the importance of pragmatic competence and are active in developing their pragmatic competence, they can make certain improvements in

the process of teaching and learning English, and it is necessary to improve their pragmatic and communicative competence. First, we need to distinguish between language form and language function in learning and teaching English. Teachers should not be content with just teaching students large amounts of vocabulary and grammar; rather, it is important that they develop some speech situations to provide students with opportunities to use their language skills. And students are required to use all opportunities to apply what they have learned, linguistic or pragmatic knowledge.

Second, when teaching English, teachers should focus on context. In the discussion above, we have seen that the same sentence can have different meanings and functions in different contexts. It is important for teachers to help students understand the unique role of context in language use.

Third, teachers should develop students' sensitivity to cultural differences in teaching English. People from different cultures can understand even the same word differently. Thus, it is acceptable to recognize that culture plays a leading role in the formation of pragmatic competence by increasing pragmatic awareness.

Commenting on communicative skills, Leung (2005) recognizes two distinct elements. These are linguistic skills that include areas such as syntax and phonology, as well as pragmatic skills that reveal the purposeful nature of the interlocutors or parties in the communication process.

"Sociolinguistic competence" used by Bachman (1990) is also one of the main parts of communicative skills and mainly consists of social and cultural rules of discourse.

It should be recognized that since the eighties of the twentieth century, the teaching of foreign languages in Uzbekistan began to move from the theoretical stage to the practical stage. The issue of form (form) in language teaching was formed especially on the basis of grammatical principles, and the dynamic feature of language, communication, communicative competence was found in textbooks in the form of monologue or dialogue in many cases.

As mentioned above, in order to better understand pragmatics both as a science and as a result/consequence of pragmatic competence, it is good to study some rules and ideas of pragmatics. The theory of speech acts is one of the fundamental (most basic) theories of pragmatics.

Pedagogical higher education institutions are distinguished by a wealth of educational materials in various fields of science, which requires a strict approach to all forms of the educational process: practical lesson, lecture, test, exam, pedagogical practice, etc.. A methodically sound, thoughtful teacher requires a creative approach to the educational process.

The existing features in the organization of the work of pedagogical higher education institutions allow this to be done at all stages of education.

REFERENCES:

1. Carstens, Adelia. 2002. Speech act theory in support of idealized warning models. In *Journal of southern African linguistics and applied language studies*, October 2002, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 191-200.
2. Cummings, L. (2005). *Pragmatics: A Multidisciplinary Perspective*. Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press.
3. Cohen, AD (2012). Teaching pragmatics in the second language classroom. *The European Journal of Applied Linguistics and TEFL*, 1(1), 35-49. Retrieved April 29, 2015 from.
4. R. Mahan Taylor (Eds.), *Teaching pragmatics*. Washington DC Office of English

Programs, U.S.Department of State. Retrieved May 30, 2014

5. Kramsch, C. (1993) Context and Culture in Language Teaching. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

6. Rasulov, Z. (2021). Reduction as the way of the language economy manifestation. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 1(1). извлечено от http://journal.buxdu.uz/index.php/journals_buxdu/article/view/2943

7. Rasulov, Z. I. ., & Saidov, K. S. . (2022). Linguistic Economy as an Inseparable Law of Language Evolution. Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes, 8–12. Retrieved from <http://www.conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/28>

